

ISic0622

The municipium honours Gaius Iulius Lon(gus?)

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

Statue base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance

On the road from the temple to city

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Segesta, excavation stores, inventory SG2018

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 77 cm

Width 60 cm

Depth 41 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

1. C(aio) Iulio C(ai) f(ilio) Lon[go]
2. duum viro
3. municipium h(onoris) [c(ausa) p(osuit)]

Apparatus

Text of Ferrua 1941

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175833

EDR 073510
EDCS 15500060

Bibliography

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